

The Question of Hybridity and the Possibility of Retaining Islamic Identity in Leila Aboulela's *The Translator*

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 06, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 28, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Orient, identity, hybridity, Leila Aboulela, The Translator, migration</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4569126</p>	<p><i>This article is an attempt to analyze the possibility of retaining one's Islamic identity within a postcolonial context in Leila Aboulela's <i>The Translator</i>. Set in Europe with a Muslim woman as its protagonist, <i>The Translator</i> is a potentially viable literary work to be approached from a postcolonial viewpoint. Sammar, a Sudanese widow who works as an Arabic translator for a Scottish Oriental scholar, with whom she later falls in love, is caught at a trans-cultural juncture, finding herself between the Orient and the Occident. This article is an attempt to investigate the cultural- and identity-confrontation between the East and the West in <i>The Translator</i> and discuss whether the protagonist, Sammar, undergoes a hybridizing process or retains her own Islamic indigenous identity. In this regard, the present article investigates Homi Bhabha's concept "hybridity" to examine its practicality or somehow impracticality concerning Muslim community living in diaspora.</i></p>

Introduction

Due to the wide range of colonization and also the vast scope of the human population affected by it, postcolonial studies has appeared as one of the most relevant subjects in the contemporary academic sphere. This significance is derived from the necessity to recognize and be aware about the main role colonization and its consequences have played within politics, culture and behavior of the colonized people and territories. Colonialism has brought numerous offshoots with which many countries are struggling. Among the most recurrent issues in this context is the relation between the colonizer and the colonized, especially during a period following decolonization in which the colonizing process is almost physically over and a great amount of cultural give and take has happened between the colonizer and the colonized.

The state of Muslim communities in the lands of the colonizers has always been a controversial and multidimensional issue. Colonial and postcolonial theorists so far have constantly tried to understand and deal with the complexities of the Muslim diaspora. Some have called for violent revolutions so as to overcome, both physically and mentally, the colonizing attitude towards the colonized and their lands; some others have stressed the biased representation of the East by the West as a means of countering the colonization process; and, finally, there are some who have emphasized the intermingling of the colonized and the colonizer and the compatibility of their cultures both as an explanation of the status quo and also as a remedy for what is generally deemed as the state of the postcolonial diasporic communities.

Leila Aboulela is a contemporary Sudanese novelist who has a mixed educational background. She was born in Egypt in 1964 to a Sudanese father and an Egyptian mother. She was brought to Sudan when she was less than two months. Aboulela lived her childhood in Sudan and she got her Master's degree in Economics at Khartoum University in 1985. Then she traveled to Aberdeen, Scotland with her husband and children, where she received an M.Sc. and MPhil in Statistics at the London School of Economics in 1990. Now, she lives in Doha, Qatar. Aboulela was a university lecturer at Aberdeen College; later she became a research assistant at the same college. She has written five novels: *The Translator* (1999), *Minaret* (2005), *Lyrics Alley* (2010), *The Kindness of Enemies* (2015) and *Bird Summons* (2019). She also wrote two collections of short stories: *Coloured Lights* (2001) and *Elsewhere, Home* (2018). Aboulela has been awarded some prizes like Caine Prize for African Writing, Scottish Mortgage Investment Trust Book Award and the Commonwealth Writers Prize. Most of her works have been translated into many languages. The main theme Aboulela deals with in her works is Muslim identity in diaspora.

Culture, Religion and Hybridity

Postcolonial studies has witnessed many significant theorists whose works provide essential segments in this area. Indeed, they represent various trends in this field of study and successfully play a notable role in contributing to postcolonial discourse. They present some authentic theories which serve to indicate many

prominent points behind the neglected voice of many nations which had been colonized and subjected to imperial power. As a result, these theories have contributed to explaining many issues and answering many questions about colonial subjects. Postcolonial theorists have been able to refute many unsubstantiated claims made by the colonial powers in regard of the colonized countries and expose their roles in the domination of the colonized and exploiting their resources and instead marketing their goods within the colonies. Among these theorists are Edward Said, Frantz Fanon, Arun P. Mukherjee, Homi K. Bhabha, Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak and Aijaz Ahmad. The present study investigates one of the most important concepts of Homi K. Bhabha, namely "hybridity", in the light of postcolonial reading of Leila Aboulela's *The Translator*.

Evidently, Bhabha holds the impressions and experiences of Poststructuralist movement as an alternative to Nationalism. The concept 'hybridity' becomes so popular and so closely associated with his name that any study of his theories would not be possible or at least complete without a deep and comprehensive study of it. Hybridity, of course, is a term that has so many meanings extended over many hundreds of years. *Oxford English Dictionary* defines it in reference to an offspring of two different racial parents. The term spread more widely during the nineteenth century as it was applied to indicate a physiological phenomenon. Nicole M. Gyulay in his article 'Hybridity' states that the origin of the term 'hybridity' refers to crossbreeding of animal or plant species aiming to create a new or a third species. He further explains that in the nineteenth century the term was used in derogatory manner that indicates people of mixed races but today the term is used to refer to mixture of cultures as a result of colonization (636). At the beginning of the emergence of the notion the Third World and during the period of the Cold War, the term hybridity occupied a wide range of studies applying the term either to migrants from Eastern societies to the West, or to the waves of modernity in the East. However, the term has occupied a vast scope in present discourses. Robert C.J. Young in his book *Colonial Desire: Hybridity in Theory, Culture and Race* shows some primal utilizations that this term had developed and describes the gradual development of the use of the term in the nineteenth century to take some meanings to be utilized within the cultural field. He contends that hybridity is an important phenomenon of a remarkable value in the colonial discourses. He further states that the process of cultural hybridity gives a chance to other marginal languages and cultures to take a place and have this contribution in the formation of a new culture and thus the process of hybridity, Young claims, weakens the unique dominance of colonial discourses (21). Stuart Hall in *Question of Cultural Identity* (1996) also argues that hybridity is an opportunity for the minority and the marginalized voice to impose itself and make an active part that represents itself among the larger groups; moreover, hybridity, he states, gives a chance to the colonized to deploy their culture and "construct visions of community, and versions of historic memory, that give narrative form to the minority positions they occupy" (Hall, et al. 58).

Homi K. Bhabha has a long deep argument on the term hybridity in one of his most widely read books, namely *The Location of Culture*. The author defines cultural hybridity as a blending process of two or more different cultures, especially the cultures of the colonizer and the colonized, to get a new culture which is somehow different from both former cultures and is independent. Bhabha holds that the hybrid feature of culture is of high significance in the postcolonial discourse. He explains that the concept of 'Hybridity' is a strategy that challenges the colonial domination; indeed, it is a strategy adopted by the colonized as a weapon to deny the imperial and colonial claims to dominance and superiority. Bhabha in his definition writes, "Hybridity is the reevaluation of the assumption of colonial identity through the repetition of discriminatory identity effects. It displays the necessary deformation and displacement of all sites of discrimination and domination" (*Location* 159).

Bhabha further argues about hybrid quality of culture and identity by exploring the elusive colonial discourse which aims at generating a gap between the "self" and the "other" (black vs. white, Muslim vs. non-Muslim, etc.). He adds that a hybrid culture is an opportunity for the "Other" to take its role in representation and to share its knowledge and thoughts and to get an authentic space within colonial discourse. So, hybridity is an occurrence that restructures and represents the denied voice of the colonized disclosing the imperial discourse and its flaws. So, according to Bhabha, hybridity is a stumbling block in front of colonialists' claims of superior "pure" culture and the gap they set between themselves and the "Other". In other words, Bhabha insists that his aim in introducing hybridity as a counter-discourse is to undermine the arrogance adopted by colonialists and their resonant claims of having a pure culture, and to give an opportunity to the "Other" to present themselves in a new form.

Homi Bhabha indeed contends that cultures are impossible to be shaped in a vacuum; rather they blend with other cultures and create new cultures. Bhabha's model reduces or even removes the differences that developed in the colonizer's method where the colonialists are differentiated from the "Other", such as what happened in India when the British imperial rulers presented themselves as the owners of "pure" culture different from the base indigenous Indian culture. The hybrid discourse, Bhabha claims, removes the differences that exist between the two cultures and challenges the narratives of colonial power and dominant culture. Byrne stating that in Bhabha's model hybridity is cultural rather than "biological or racial". She argues, "Cultural hybridity is theorised as the result of the continual process of translation which is internal to any culture, which in turn stems from an apprehension of cultural difference" (33). Selden et al. also hold that for Bhabha hybridity "reverses the

effects of the colonialist disavowal [of difference], so that other 'denied' knowledges enter upon the dominant discourse and estrange the basis of its authority" (qtd. in Selden, et al. 227).

Although many critics and scholars endorse and follow Homi Bhabha's cultural hybridity as a theory, there are some others who look with doubt at and even question his theory, such as Aijaz Ahmad, Benita Parry and Abdul JanMohamed. They argue that Bhabha by focusing mainly on the colonial announcement without mentioning the material condition of colonial power has limited the significance and validity of his theory. Critics like Abdul JanMohamed and Benita Parry, as Loomba states, accuse Bhabha "of neglecting material conditions of colonial rule by concentrating on colonial representations" (Loomba 104). Ahmad also argues that hybridity as a postcolonial condition leaves wider gaps behind in Bhabha's attempt to approach the problems as being homogeneous among different cultures. He also holds, according to Gyulay, that "the idea of hybridity as a shared condition within the postcolonial world is an example of how postcolonial theory can have a tendency to homogenize the widely different cultures it addresses" (Gyulay 637).

Aijaz Ahmad divides hybridity into cultural and philosophical or even political hybridity; he expresses his endorsement of the former and states that the main idea which shapes the cultural notion of hybridity is founded on a clear fact: "the traffic among modern cultures is now so brisk that one can hardly speak of discrete national cultures that are not fundamentally transformed by that traffic" (Ahmad 371). However, he shows his disagreement with hybridity as "a generalized condition of postcoloniality into which all contemporary cultures are now irretrievably ushered" (ibid). Ahmad adds that in that case the migrant intellectual, especially one who resides in the center of the metropolis, "comes to signify a universal condition of hybridity and is said to be the subject of Truth that individuals living within their national cultures do not possess" (ibid).

Banita Parry critiques Homi Bhabha's methodology as well as that of Spivak and contends that their theories do not serve much for postcolonial texts ("Problems in Current Theories of Colonial Discourse" 10). Parry sees that Bhabha's approach is a kind of reducing or undermining the earlier role which is ascribed to the postcolonial intellectuals and native voice. So it denies the history of culture which is at the very roots of a nation's identity (ibid). She praises rather Fanon for his steady writing in regard of decolonization and disobedience to imperial domination. Parry emphasizes the role of the intellectuals in holding to the primacy of enunciation rather than being subaltern. In other words, she claims that cultural hybridity is oppressing both to the native and intellectuals (10).

Hybridity and Islamic Identity

Since any literary author cannot dispense with the notion of "reality" in his or her works, regardless of the amount of flexibility reality may have, any literary depiction of the Muslim diasporic community inevitably contains certain amount of Islamic and traditional principles, whether the author is friendly or hostile to religious and traditional principles. In so far as Leila Aboulela concerned, religion and tradition play a central and a crucial role in the lives of the characters in her fictional works. The present study has chosen *The Translator* as a fair model that negotiates the diasporic Muslim identity. Sammar, the main character, is a Sudanese Muslim widow living in Scotland. She has recently lost her husband in a car accident. Although she had passed a hard time, being lonely and away from her warm hearted family and friends, she could preserve her identity and live as a Muslim. Four years have passed since the death of her husband, leaving her lonely with her sadness, and the only five times prayers were her solace in a foreign country.

Sammar could play an active role during her job as a Translator within Rae's department at Aberdeen University. Rae is a Scottish secular professor and expert in Middle East Studies. The translation from Arabic to English of Islamic documents and also Quranic texts and Prophetic hadith to be published in European magazines was Sammar's work. In other words, *The Translator* is the story of a faithful woman who could present a wonderful example that embodied the personality of a woman who traveled from an Eastern Muslim country to a European country where she lived for some years, and worked and mixed with the Europeans. Although she was living alone, she did not stop from being with people, and more importantly she was able to preserve her Eastern identity and did not abandon her values and customs. She not only maintained her identity but also communicated in the best way with a European society and benefited from that culture and traditions. At this point Aboulela was able to question Homi Bhabha's claim that an Oriental person cannot live in the West without undergoing a cultural experience, which cannot happen without abandoning some of his/her customs and values and merging with the Western culture and traditions.

The most striking thing about Sammar's character is that she was brought up in an Islamic cultured family that has given her an ability to distinguish between the right Islamic principles and the distorted form of those traditions and principles. During her work in Rae's office, she explains to him many of the Islamic principles and rules which have been distorted and corrupted by extremists. She conveys two main sources of Islamic principles: The holy Quran and the Prophetic hadith. Sammar successfully presents a worthy message that says not each Islamic community that professes Islam has the right to embody all Muslims. Islam is a religion of peace that seeks the goodness of its followers and all people, not as some extremists try to depict it.

Sammar reported to Rae about some documents he gave her to translate that they belonged to an extremist group that claims Islam. She comes to find some faults with this group and explains:

There is something pathetic about the spelling mistakes, the stain on the paper in spite of the bravado. There are truths but they are detached, not tied to reality . . . There is no recourse in the Sharia for what they're doing, however much they try and justify themselves. (Aboulela 26)

Yearning for the past characterizes Sammar and her love of Eastern traditions as she keeps remembering her girlish and youth period when she was living in Sudan. Indeed, Sammar's love to her native country and traditions is a part of her identity, but what has brought her again to the West is to run away of the troubles with her mother-in-law, or it may be the sadness that captured her in her native country after returning alone and having lost her husband in a car accident. In Sudan everything around her reminds her of her lovely deceased husband. She always thinks of people and the events that happened around her in Sudan, especially the very time when she had arrived Sudan at the age of seven to live with her aunt there.

In Scotland and after spending some time working for her boss, Sammar falls in love with the non-Muslim Rae. However, she refuses to be on more intimate relationship with him without the legal bond of marriage since Islamic principles do not allow her to get married to a non-Muslim. She, therefore, asks him to convert into Islam. Rae refuses to become a Muslim and Sammar in consequence leaves him and her job and returns home. Thus, Sammar manifests her commitment to Islam as a fundamental part of her identity. She does not act in accordance with Bhabha's conceptual theory and hybridity in particular and shows it is inapplicable to members of the Muslim community in diaspora. Taken as an appropriate example for Muslims living in the West, Sammar successfully retains her Islamic identity and continues observing the religious rituals like the five times prayers, wearing hijab and reciting the holy Quran. She goes to the student mosque, though located in another building far from her Department, to attend the afternoon prayer performed collectively with other students. She is regularly praying her five times prayers whether she is at the job or in her flat. During the time that the study year is about to finish and a holiday nearly to be started, she goes to the chapel and pray alone. She is confident about what she is practicing of Islamic traditions, such as the five time prayers, fasting, breaking her fast with some dates and yogurt as recommended by the Prophet, and keeping the remembrance of Allah (tasbeeh) after each prayer. (The way that Muslims mention the Almighty Allah when they finish their prayer as an act of acknowledging His grace). In relation to her boss, Rae, and his suggestion to spare some time for driving together, she shows her disagreement to that and to being alone with him. She explains to him that it is against Islamic principles and her religious beliefs. One of the Islamic teachings recommends Muslims in face of hard times or misery to be patient, to remember Allah and to entreat Him to pass this hard time. Sammar follows this lesson successfully at the time of affliction. On the death of her husband she keeps repeating, "Only Allah is eternal, only Allah is eternal. . . Temporary, this life is temporary, fleeting" (9). In her loneliness and in the middle of her sadness caused by the death of her husband, Sammar finds a great solace in the Islamic five daily prayers: "Hours flitting away like minutes. Days in which the only things she could rouse herself to do was pray the five prayers. They were the only challenge, the last touch with normality, without them she would have fallen, lost awareness of the shift of day into night" (16).

Furthermore, Sammar despite her unyielding commitment to Islamic principles, she never deals with people around her as strangers holding other norms and belonging to other culture, but she mixes with and accompanies them in a friendly manner. In the University where she works, Sammar shares a room with Diana and is interested in talking to her and be familiar with her culture. She shows a great deal of interest in talking with Ph.D. students, especially those who are under Rae's supervision. Although Sammar suffers because of Lesley, her noisy neighbor, who inhabits the ground floor, she is so kind and polite to address her as Aunt (32). Sammar is also attracted to and fascinated—though sometimes is shocked—by some of the European customs and traditions. When Rae, for example, went to see his daughter Mhairi in Edinburgh, he stayed in the house of his ex-wife's parents where his daughter was spending her holiday. This was a "Culture-shock for Sammar"; however, she considered this event as "civilized behaviour, an amicable divorce" (38). She is also interested in way things were put in order and organized in Scotland which was missing or lost in her country. Likewise, Sammar likes the architecture deployed in their buildings and "the way the grass curved upwards to the road, the white dome of Engineering shaped like a mosque" (105).

Leila Aboulela in *The Translator* presents some other Muslim figures such as Yasmin, Sammar's only friend and the other employee who works in the same Department with her as Rae's secretary. Yasmin is a committed Muslim woman who retains her Eastern and Islamic identity in diaspora. She continually advises Sammar to keep distant from Rae and not to be too intimate with him because he is a secular man and there is no hope for her to be married to him. Once she asked Sammar, "Are you expecting him to become a Muslim so he could marry you?" (74) or if she was "going to marry someone who's not a Muslim?" "Of course not," Sammar answered, "that would be against the sharia" (92).

One of the striking things about Aboulela's novel is the way she shows how the extremist Muslims distort and corrupt the noble teachings and principles of Islam. She accomplishes this goal in two ways: explaining the true Islamic principles and discrediting the false pretensions of the extremists who claim they represent Islam. Moreover, she writes back showing the ignorance or malice of those who attack the Muslims accusing them of being behind and the perpetrators of dire events such as 9/11 (the Two Trade Towers Attack) that led to treat the Muslims, especially those living in diaspora, as hostages or at least with discrimination and inferiority. In this regard, Sammar represents an authentic and steady figure that keeps her Islamic principles and faith. It may be concluded that retaining one's culture and religious beliefs and other elements of identity is possible so far that they would trespass on the freedom of others or violate their rights. Most of these religious practices are personal and depend on one's confidence to exercise or follow them. So there is no need to be committed to Bhabhaian theory, at least not always, of cultural hybridity which leads to losing one's authentic and pure identity.

Conclusion

Contrary to Homi Bhabha's claim that cultural hybridity is the best method to integrate two different cultures, the cultures of the colonizer and the colonized, and reduce the gap between them, Leila Aboulela looks at the question from another perspective which is adopted by Sammar, the main character of her novel *The Translator*. Sammar is a Muslim woman living in the West, and in her life journey within the non-Muslim society she tries to retain her Islamic identity and be a practicing Muslim. She is not isolated from the European society and works and deals with many different classes of people who are non-Muslim. She has been able to keep her Islamic identity, wearing scarf, performing the five times prayer, and abstaining from drinking alcohol or to be married to a non-Muslim. The study concludes that Muslims may live in a diasporic condition while retaining their Islamic identity and be practicing Muslims.

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